

The Environmental Data Service

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NERC data centres are working together

Last year NERC commissioned all the data centres as a single service. It's been business as usual, but we are now planning for things we can do together.

The data centres involved are:

National Geoscience Data Centre (NGDC)

Environmental Information Data Centre (EIDC)

British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC)

Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA)

Polar Data Centre (PDC)

Shared Services

We already share some services, like the NERC data catalogue. We will be improving current services and rolling out others where it looks appropriate, for instance the Environmental Work Bench developed by CEH.

Shared Expertise

Many of the data centres have specialities that we can learn from. For example, BODC has been managing vocabularies since 1969.

Shared Platforms

Where it makes sense we can use shared compute, storage and other resources. We are starting work on a shared deposit service for datasets made of large files that will utilise JASMIN storage.

Image Under Construction

Currently the data centres look and feel disconnected. We will be looking at offering some visual clues that we belong to a single service and improve navigation between services. At the same time we don't want to add to this mess!

We want to look coherent and clear. How do you think we should do that? Add a post-it note if you have any ideas or comments.

Innovation

NERC had hoped to commission an innovation part to compliment this data service, however this has been delayed. When it does get going we will be required to serve a wider community including business and government agencies.

